

Interview Flyhistorisk Museum Sola
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Name: Michaela Florescu
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WP2. Investigating the conservation of WWII wrecks (land or underwater), and more particularly parts made of Al alloys.

• Presentation of the institution:

Flyhistorisk Museum, Sola (Sola Aviation Museum) is an aviation museum located in Stavanger Airport, Sola, near Stavanger, Norway. The museum was founded in 1984 and is run by local volunteers. Flyhistorisk Museum, Sola became part of Jærmuseet in January 2012.

The museum is housed in an old aircraft hangar at the former seaplane base at Stavanger Airport, built by German labour during World War II.

The collection of the museum includes civilian, military and general aviation aircraft. Stavanger Lufthavn, Sola was the maintenance hub for Braathens S.A.F.E and Helikopter Service. The airport was also an active airforce base for Luftwaffe during World War II and for Royal Norwegian Air Force during the cold war. The museum has primarily concentrated its exhibition around its local history.

The museum has an extensive collection of German World War II aircraft, and of aircrafts used by the Royal Norwegian Air Force including some trainers.

(source: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Flyhistorisk_Museum,_Sola)

The museum, through the Association of Friends of the Sola Aviation Museum (Flyhistorisk Museum Sola ved Venneforeningen), was involved in the recovery and conservation projects for a Heinkel 115 wreck (see Form A and attached reports).

• The operating chain: from the wreck to the museum

At what stage or stages of the operating chain has (or is) the institution/ group / association been involved? Defining a recovery project? Integrating wrecks or artefacts from wrecks in the collection? Do they have direct input in defining the projects or just executing? What is their approach? Is it similar or different approach if different projects?

The recovery of the Heinkel 115 was carried out by the Association of Friends of the Sola Aviation Museum. The Heinkel 115 had been found in 2005, and a first, unsuccessful, attempt to raise it from the water took place in 2007-2008. A new, better planned attempt, succeeded in 2012. The success of this attempt relied on better preparation, with plans made for temporary storage of the wreck in a custom-made freshwater tank, appropriate participants and support

from sponsors, financial or in kind (goods, services) to ensure also the conservation after recovery.

In the past, the museum had dealt with another wreck, a Messerschmitt Bf 109 (very typical German aircraft from WWII, commonly flown in Norway after 1940).

This wreck, on the contrary of the Heinkel 115, was a random find by 2 fishermen in 1988.

This wreck was in very bad condition, and also because of the conditions of the recovery, it was not clearly identified and related to an event. Important parts, like the engine, were missing.

It arrived at Flyhistorisks Museum Sola after the Norwegian State declined interest in it for the Defense Museums group.

- Concept of "conservation": Do you think of long-term preservation/conservation of the artefacts you handle? How do you define long term? What does the idea of "conservation" mean to you for this kind of heritage? How would you want that heritage to be passed on to future generations? Has that definition shifted over time for you/the institution?

The conservation approach has changed very much between the two wrecks.

Work on the Messerschmitt Bf 109 was more about remaking and replacing a lot of the parts, and on the contrary, the approach for the Heinkel 115 was much more to keep it as it was, as far as possible.

Some of the participants were different, and projects were very distant in time, but the main reason for this difference is the condition of the wrecks and the circumstances for the recovery.

- Who works on these collections (after recovery): conservators, technical staff (aviation background or not), volunteers? What training for these different stakeholders? Do they work in collaboration? Are they internal or external to the museum? What is the relationship between museum management / conservation and the people in charge of interventions directly? (addition to Form A)

The museum is operated by volunteers. All are retirees and have connection with aeronautics or military before (mechanics, pilots, etc...).

For the Heinkel 115 project, a conservator was involved part time. (see form A and attached reports).

- Conditions of conservation of the collection / artefact: aircraft in working order with regular maintenance / complete planes (or nearly) with or without preventive conservation / wrecks or elements of wrecks: exposed or not, kept in storage / outdoors (addition to Form A)?

Conservation on the Heinkel 115 is still not completed. Work on the tail section and the engine is completed, those two parts are on display. The other parts are either in the workshop undergoing interventions, or in storage.

The rest of the collection includes complete aircrafts from various periods.

There are no preventive conservation protocols.

- Conditions of storage location (exhibition room or storage): rooms or hall? awareness about influence of climate on preservation? Monitoring or not of HR & T ° and their changes during the year (addition to Form A)?

Both exhibition hall and storage hall are old buildings reused by the museum, but they are not meeting museum standards: no climate control, no light control no pollutants monitoring.

The location of the museum is close to Stavanger Airport.

The volunteers are aware of the influence of climate control on the conservation of aluminum parts.

- Reflecting on their own practice: do you feel that you know everything you would like to when it comes to managing this sort of artefacts? What would be the aspects you would like to know more about? Do you keep informed or in contact with other stakeholders in this field? Has your practice evolved through those connections?

The general purpose for the Heinkel was to be as little interventive as possible, especially because of the very good condition of the wreck after recovery. But the volunteers are aware that the parts of the wreck that have not been treated yet are deteriorating visibly, and corrosion issues with aluminium alloys have appeared in time, whereas they didn't exist initially. This is because storage conditions are not appropriate, meaning, no controlled climate and important fluctuation in RH and temperature during the year (winter/summer). The volunteers are aware that this forces them to be more interventive than they would have wished, as they now must replace some parts severely deteriorated after recovery.

- Conservation problem that may be encountered with Al alloys (questions and needs if there are any, or practices for solving these problems)? Does it feel like a priority concern regarding your corpus of WWII wrecks? regarding the rest of the collection (if relevant)? What type of treatment protocols are (or have been) carried out (addition to Form A)?

The wreck was in very good condition when it was recovered (see details in Form A and attached reports). Aluminium alloys showed very little corrosion at the time of recovery. Corrosion was more important on magnesium alloys and ferrous parts. See attached Form A for details on treatments.

- Promotion of WWII aeronautical heritage, influence of the country's history in the conflict and the relationship to that history?

The museum's focus is on local aviation history. Because Stavanger airport was a German base during WWII, this period is important for local history. The Heinkel 115 is also of particular interest because of the very good conservation condition of the wreck.